

Kinetics and Mechanism of Oxidation of Benzoin and its Derivatives by Acid-Dichromate

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The kinetics of oxidation of benzoin and substituted benzoin by acid dichromate have been investigated in acetic acid-water mixture. The reaction shows first order dependence on the concentrations of both Cr(VI) and substrate. The reaction is acid catalysed and the order with respect to sulphuric acid concentration is two. The reaction rate is not affected by changing the concentrations of both sulphate and bisulphate ions. HCrO_4^- is considered to be the active oxidant. Evidence for the complex formation between the oxidant and the substrate has been indicated. The order of reactivity in different mineral acids follows the sequence: $\text{HClO}_4 > \text{H}_2\text{SO}_4 > \text{HCl}$. Addition of Mn(II) retards the rate of the reaction considerably. Activation parameters have been evaluated and structure-reactivity relationships discussed. The results are accommodated by considering the reaction to take place between enol form of the ketone and the oxidant via Cr(VI)-ester which subsequently decomposes in the rate determining step to give the product.

THOUGH chromic acid (CrO_3) oxidation of some acyloins¹ has been reported in the literature, the kinetics and mechanism of the oxidation of benzoin by acid dichromate have not been investigated. Since the kinetics of the oxidation and mechanism depend on the Cr(VI)-species present in the reaction medium, the present investigation on the oxidation of benzoin and its derivatives by acid dichromate has been attempted in detail.

Experimental

Materials and Methods :

Cr(VI) solution was prepared from AnalaR potassium dichromate. Benzoin used were prepared according to the method described in an earlier paper². Acetic acid used as the solvent was of S. Merck, G.R. grade. Demineralised distilled water was used for preparing the solvent mixture. All other chemicals used were of either AnalaR or G.R. grade.

Kinetic measurement :

Kinetic experiments were initiated by mixing equal volumes of two solutions (both being pre-equilibrated at the reaction temperature), one containing dichromate solution and the other organic substrate dissolved in acetic acid. The reactions were conducted at constant acidity and ionic strength. The course of the reaction was followed by withdrawing a known volume (5 cc) of the reaction mixture at definite intervals of time into a flask containing known excess of ferrous ammonium sulphate. The excess of Fe^{2+} was titrated with standard

potassium dichromate solution using N-phenyl anthranilic acid indicator.

The [substrate] was always taken in sufficient excess over [Cr(VI)] so that observed kinetics were pseudo-first order. The first order rate constant was calculated from the slope of the linear plot of $\log [\text{oxidant}]_t$ against time. These plots were linear for about 70% of the reaction. The duplicate rate measurements were reproducible to $\pm 3\%$. The energy of activation was calculated by least square method from the values of $\log k_{\text{obs}}$ and $1/T$. Thermodynamic parameters were calculated using Eyring's equation.

Stoichiometry and Product analysis :

The stoichiometry of the reaction was found by allowing a known excess of acid dichromate solution to react with benzoin in 50% binary mixture of acetic acid-water (v/v) for 48 hours. A blank experiment without the substrate was also simultaneously run to take into account the consumption of Cr(VI) by the solvent. Unused Cr(VI) was determined. The result indicates consumption of one mole of benzoin for 0.34 mole of dichromate. Benzil was found to be the product of oxidation which was identified by mixed melting point and IR spectra. The overall reaction for benzoin oxidation may be represented by the following empirical equation :

The stoichiometry for the reaction of deoxybenzoin and dichromate was also determined. The

mole ratio was 1 : 0.67 and the product of the oxidation was also identified to be benzil.

Results and Discussion

Oxidation of benzoïn by acid dichromate has been studied in binary solvent mixture of acetic acid and water (50% v/v) at constant acidity and ionic strength. Dependence of the rate on the concentrations of the reactants has been incorporated in Table 1. The order with respect to the concentration

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF VARYING [SUBSTRATE] AND [OXIDANT] AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES

[H₂SO₄] = 0.125M, μ = 0.15M, HOAc-H₂O (50% v/v).

[Cr(VI)] × 10 ⁴ M	[Benzoin] × 10 ³ M	k ₁ × 10 ⁴ sec ⁻¹			
		35°	40°	45°	50°
5.0	0.5	3.6	4.45	6.0	8.8
5.0	0.725	4.5	5.73	7.75	11.0
5.0	1.0	5.26	6.6	9.2	13.3
5.0	1.25	6.3	7.85	10.6	15.4
5.0	2.5	11.0	13.2	18.3	22.53
5.5	1.0	5.38	—	—	—
7.15	1.0	5.30	—	—	—
8.30	1.0	5.21	—	—	—
10.0	1.0	5.35	—	—	—

of Cr(VI) and concentration of benzoïn was observed to be one each. Second order rate constants (k₂ × 10³M⁻¹sec⁻¹) calculated from the slopes of the linear plots of k_{obs} vs [substrate] are 3.2, 4.53, 5.34, 8.8 at 35, 40, 45 and 50° respectively.

The plots of 1/k_{obs} vs 1/[Benzoin] at different temperatures are linear and do not pass through the origin but show definite intercepts at 1/k_{obs} axis. This indicates kinetic evidence for complex formation between the oxidant and the substrate. This complex formation has been also confirmed from conductance measurement which indicates 1:1 complex formation between Cr(VI)-species and benzoïn under the experimental conditions. From the intercepts and slopes of the above plots, the values of the rate constants (k_d) for the disproportionation of Cr(VI)-benzoïn complex and the values of equilibrium constant (K) for the formation of the complex have been calculated respectively at different temperatures. The values of K (lit. mole⁻¹) are 7.6, 8.1, 8.5 and 10.3 at 35, 40, 45 and 50° respectively. Enthalpy and entropy of activation associated with the complex formation are -4.1 K cal/mole and -12.4 E.U. respectively. Similarly, the values of rate constants for the disproportionation of the complex (k_d × 10³ sec⁻¹) are 1.3, 1.6, 2.1 and 3.3 respectively at the above temperatures. ΔE[‡] and ΔS[‡] for the decomposition of the complex are 14.5 K cal/mole and -25 E.U. respectively. These data show that the complex has a rigid structure and it is formed by an exothermic process.

Effect of varying [H₂SO₄] :

The oxidation of benzoïn by Cr(VI) has also been studied at various concentrations of sulphuric acid, potassium bisulphate and potassium sulphate. These results are incorporated in Table 2. The

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF VARYING [H₂SO₄], [HSO₄⁻] and [SO₄²⁻] at 35°C. [Benzoin] = 1 × 10⁻³M, [Cr(VI)] = 5 × 10⁻⁴M, HOAc : H₂O (50% v/v)

[H ₂ SO ₄] × 10M	[KHSO ₄] × 10M	[K ₂ SO ₄] × 10M	K ₁ × 10 ⁴ sec ⁻¹
0.5	—	—	0.70
1.0	—	—	2.85
1.25	—	—	5.26
1.25	0.75	—	5.30
1.25	1.25	—	5.32
1.25	1.50	—	5.30
1.25	3.00	—	5.43
1.25	—	0.5	5.22
1.25	—	1.0	5.35
1.25	—	1.5	5.38
1.25	—	3.0	5.46
1.5	—	—	6.4
2.0	—	—	11.2
2.5	—	—	19.8
20.0	—	—	95.0
20.0	—	—	0.38*

* The value of rate constant refers to the oxidation of deoxybenzoïn.

reaction is found to be acid catalysed. Plot of log k_{obs} vs log [H₂SO₄] is linear and the order of the reaction with respect to the concentration of the acid is two. 1/k_{obs} vs 1/[H₂SO₄] is also linear and has a definite intercept on 1/k_{obs} axis. The rate of the reaction is not appreciably affected by increasing the concentrations of either HSO₄⁻ or SO₄²⁻. All these facts show that H⁺ is only responsible for rate increase when sulphuric acid concentration is increased.

Effect of varying solvent composition :

To find out the nature of Cr(VI) species participating in the reaction, the rate of oxidation has been studied in varying compositions of acetic acid-water mixture. The rate of the reaction has been found to increase with increasing acetic acid content in the solvent mixture and the data for the oxidation of benzoïn are recorded in Table 3. The plot of log k vs the reciprocal of dielectric constant has been observed to be linear with a positive slope

TABLE 3—EFFECT OF VARYING SOLVENT COMPOSITION

[Cr(VI)] = 5 × 10⁻⁴M, [Benzoin] = 10⁻³M, μ = 0.15M, [H₂SO₄] = 0.125M, T = 35°C

% of HOAc (v/v)	10 ³ /D	k ₁ × 10 ⁴ sec ⁻¹
40	22.38	4.47
50	26.04	5.26
60	31.70	7.08
70	37.50	9.57
80	45.60	14.57
90	53.60	23.19

indicating a positive ion-dipole reaction. Considering a monopositive Cr(VI)-species as the active oxidant, the value of 'r', the minimum distance of approach between the ion and the dipole has been calculated to be 0.7Å from the slope of the above plot. This value is of expected magnitude.

Nature of Cr(VI)-species :

It is difficult to decide the exact molecular identity of Cr(VI) species present in the solution since it is involved in a series of protolytic and hydrolytic equilibria, e.g.,

In addition to the above species, HCrO_3^+ is known to combine with HSO_4^- in sulphuric acid medium to form⁹ a superior oxidising species $\text{HCrO}_3\text{HSO}_4^-$. Acetyl chromate ion (AcOCrO_3^-) may also exist in the reaction medium containing high percentage of acetic acid. Out of all the above Cr(VI) species, the possibility of a neutral or a negative Cr(VI) species participating in the reaction may be ruled out as the results on acid effect and dielectric dependence on rate indicate the involvement of a positively charged Cr(VI)-species. In the present oxidation $[\text{Cr(VI)}] \leq 3 \times 10^{-5} \text{M}$ and therefore whole of dichromate is expected to be present in the form of bichromate ion⁴. This bichromate ion possibly combines with H^+ to form a superior oxidising species, HCrO_3^+ . This is a more probable electron acceptor as the electron accepting property of O-Cr bond is enhanced by the presence of a positive charge. Formation of such a species of Cr(VI) is also in accord with the second order rate dependence on acid concentration.

Effect of addition of Mn^{2+} :

The rate data for the effect of adding Mn^{2+} have been recorded in Table 4. The rate-decreases considerably by increasing the concentration of Mn^{2+} .

TABLE 4—RATE DEPENDENCE ON Mn^{2+}

$[\text{Cr(VI)}] = 5 \times 10^{-4} \text{M}$, $[\text{Benzoin}] = 10^{-3} \text{M}$, $[\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4] = 0.125 \text{M}$,
 $\text{HOAc} : \text{H}_2\text{O}$ (50% v/v), $t_r = 35^\circ\text{C}$

$[\text{Mn(II)}] \times 10^3 \text{M}$	0	7.5	10	12.5
$k_1 \times 10^4 \text{sec}^{-1}$	5.26	2.02	1.58	1.46

This is indicative of the formation of some lower valent chromium species⁵⁻⁸. Reduction of rate by addition of Mn(II) is expected if it catalyses the disproportionation of intermediate valency states of chromium and suggests that Cr(IV) is probably involved as intermediate. In addition to this effect, retardation by Mn(II) may also be explained by

assuming the formation of an unreactive complex⁷ between Mn(II) and the substrate.

Effect of different mineral acids on rate :

The rate data for the oxidation of benzoin by Cr(VI) in different acids have been recorded in Table 5 along with the thermodynamic parameters. The free energy of activation for the reaction in each acid is of the same order of magnitude indicating a common reaction path. The order of reactivity follows the sequence :

This order of reactivity is in consonance with the electron withdrawing capacities of the anions of the acids. The negative ions like ClO_4^- , HSO_4^- and Cl^- increase the tendency of the Cr(VI)-species to accept electrons from the substrate. Since ClO_4^- is more electron withdrawing than HSO_4^- and Cl^- , the rate of oxidation in perchloric acid medium is more compared to reactions in other two acid media.

Structure-Reactivity Relation :

The rate data of substituted benzoin at different temperatures have been also recorded in Table 5. Arrhenius equation has been found to be valid within the temperature range studied. The reactivity of the substituted benzoin conforms to the following order :

The logarithm of the rate constants at 35° correlate well with σ values⁹. The value of ρ is 1.14. This indicates a relatively electron-rich carbon centre in the transition state of the reaction. The above order of reactivity is in agreement with the electronic effect of the substituents. The values of entropy of activation indicate rigid transition states. A common mechanism is envisaged for the substituted benzoin as the free energy of activation values are of the same order of magnitude.

Mechanism :

A ketone may react directly or through its enol in oxidation reactions. Direct oxidations⁹⁻¹¹ by cobaltic, manganic and ceric salts have been shown to involve one electron change and seem to have a free radical mechanism. In the present oxidation, no induced polymerization of acrylonitrile or reduction of HgCl_2 has been seen. Hence a free radical mechanism is ruled out. Oxidations proceeding via enol intermediates^{9,12-13} have been reported for two electron oxidants like Tl(III) , Pb(IV) and Hg(II) . Benzoin and substituted benzoin in aqueous acid medium remain as equilibrium mixture of enol and keto forms. Cr(VI) species can abstract

TABLE 5—KINETIC AND THERMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS IN PRESENCE OF DIFFERENT ACIDS

[Substrate] = $10^{-2}M$, [Cr(VI)] = $5 \times 10^{-4}M$, [Acid] = $0.125M$ $\mu = 0.15M$, HOAc - H_2O (50% v/v)

Nuclear substituent	$k_1 \times 10^4 \text{ sec}^{-1}$					ΔE^\ddagger K cal/mole	ΔH^\ddagger K cal/mole	ΔG^\ddagger K cal/mole	$-\Delta S^\ddagger$ E.U.
	30°	35°	40°	45°	50°				
<i>In sulphuric acid :</i>									
4-OCH ₃	—	2.51	3.03	4.07	4.86	9.1	8.50	23.3	48.0
4-OH	—	2.95	3.99	5.50	7.1	11.9	11.3	23.2	36.4
H	3.36	5.26	6.6	9.2	13.3	13.9	13.3	22.8	31.0
4-Cl	—	9.58	11.97	16.88	23.97	12.4	11.8	22.4	37.0
2,2'-dinitro	—	18.56	26.1	38.8	57.78	16.2	15.6	22.0	20.9
<i>In Hydrochloric acid :</i>									
H	1.11	1.52	2.3	2.83	3.99	12.8	12.2	23.6	37.0
<i>In Perchloric acid :</i>									
H	6.97	8.51	12.72	16.65	21.47	11.4	10.8	22.5	38.1

electrons from the enediol with more facility in preference to the keto form. The reaction through enediol finds further support from the study of the electrolytic oxidation of phenylacetylenes¹⁴, where it has been concluded that stilbenediol diacetate is the precursor to benzil. Formation of enol is, however, not rate determining as the observed rate is not independent of [Cr(VI)]. In view of the above discussion, a probable mechanism consistent with the results has been suggested involving the reaction between the enol and the active oxidant $HCrO_3^+$ via the formation of an acyclic chromic ester which subsequently decomposes in the rate determining step to give the product. Attack of $HCrO_3^+$ on enediol system is further supported by the fact that the oxidation of olefinic compounds¹⁵ also involves this positively charged active species of Cr(VI). The probable course of the reaction is outlined below :

Now by applying steady state approximation to the concentration of the Cr(VI)-ester, the above scheme leads to the rate expression :

$$\frac{-d[Cr(VI)]}{dt} = k_1[Cr(VI)] \text{ when } [Benzoin] \gg [Cr(VI)] \text{ at constant } [H^+].$$

Hence, the proposed mechanism is valid as the reaction follows first order kinetics in [Cr(VI)].

The effect of substituents can also be explained satisfactorily by the above mechanism. Electron donating groups retard the rate as the transition state is destabilized and the opposite effect is observed by electron withdrawing groups because of the stabilization of the transition state. Benzoine reacts faster than deoxybenzoine under the same experimental conditions (Table 2). Since the product of oxidation of benzoine and deoxybenzoine is same, deoxybenzoine is expected to get oxidised through benzoine. The rate constant for the oxidation of deoxybenzoine to benzoine has been evaluated to be $3.5 \times 10^{-6} \text{ sec}^{-1}$ according to the method described by Anantaraman and Nair¹⁶. The slow rate of oxidation of deoxybenzoine compared to benzoine can be explained in terms of the stability of the concerned Cr(VI)-ester. The ester from benzoine gets easily decomposed to benzil by an intramolecular rearrangement whereas, the corresponding ester from deoxybenzoine cannot be decomposed to benzoine by a similar process. It requires the participation of water from the solvent mixture. Hence, the rate of oxidation of deoxybenzoine is slow.

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